

Synthesis and Fungitoxicity of some Halogeno-Polynitrophenyl Esters of N,N'-(2-Methyl)-, N,N'-Methyl and N,N'-Phenyl Piperizino-Dithioformic Acids.

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Forty-six halogenonitrophenyl esters of N,N'-(2-methyl)-, N,N'-methyl and N,N'-phenyl-piperizino-dithioformic acids have been obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes and sodium salt of substituted dithioformic acids. They have been tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Colletotrichum gloeosporides* by spore germination method. A relation between fungitoxicity and structure has also been established.

POLYNITROARYL esters of N-substituted aminoformic acids are used as antifungal agents^{1,2} and as accelerators in rubber vulcanisation^{3,4}. In view of the wide range of fungicidal activity of these compounds and their use in industry, the work⁵ has now been extended to the synthesis of a number of polynitrophenyl esters of N,N'-(2-methyl)-, N,N'-methyl and N,N'-phenyl piperizino-dithioformic acids.

4,6-dinitro-, 3-chloro-2-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 4-chloro-5-methyl-2,6-dinitrophenyl ester of N,N'-(2-methyl) (Table 1), N,N'-methyl (Table 2) and N,N'-phenyl (Table 3) piperizino dithioformic acids respectively.

Infra-red Spectrum

The structure of these compounds is supported by infrared spectral results. The infrared bands at

The esters III have been prepared by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes (I) with sodium salt of N-substituted dithioformic acid (II) in ethanolic solution at 0°-5°. Thus 1-chloro-2,4-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,6-dinitro⁶, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-, 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro⁷, 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro⁸, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro⁹, 1-chloro-2-methyl-4,6-dinitro¹⁰, 1-chloro-3-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-4-methyl-2,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-5-methyl-2,4,6-trinitro¹¹, 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitro¹², 1,2-dichloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro¹³, 1,2-dichloro-5-methyl-4,6-dinitro¹⁴, 1,3-dichloro-2-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, and 1,4-dichloro-5-methyl-2,6-dinitrobenzenes¹⁵ on condensation with the sodium salts of N,N'-(2-methyl)-, N,N'-methyl and N,N'-phenyl piperizino dithioformic acids gave 2,4-dinitro-, 2,6-dinitro-, 2,4,6-trinitro-, 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-, 4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-, 2-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 3-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 4-methyl-2,6-dinitro-, 5-methyl-2,4,6-trinitro-, 2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-5-methyl-4,6-dinitro-, 2-bromo-5-methyl-

1350, 700 and 650 indicate the presence of nitrogroup, chlorine and bromine atom. The C = N stretching frequency is observed at 1500 and 1480 respectively. The lowering of the C = N stretching frequency is an indication of the coordination of nitrogen atom with sulphur atom and thus showing less double bond character in the C = N bond

These compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria tenuis*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Colletotrichum gloeosporides* by spore germination method¹⁶. The dosages in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ required for the inhibition of 50% growth of fungi have been recorded (Table 1, 2 and 3).

TABLE 1—ESTERS OF N,N'-(2-METHYL)-PIPERIZINO-BIS-DITHIO-FORMIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		Dosages required for the inhibition of 50% of growth in $\mu\text{ gm/cm}^2$			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	AN	AT	HS	CG
1.	2,4-DNP	79	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	39.00	39.04	2.75	2.74	107	82	108	108
2.	2,6-DNP	92	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	39.02	39.04	2.71	2.74	100	93	93	94
3.	2,4,6-DNP	116	78	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₄	33.78	33.80	2.10	2.08	93	80	93	93
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	119	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	34.92	34.90	2.15	2.13	83	75	75	75
5.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	115	75	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	34.87	34.90	2.16	2.13	150	235	152	130
6.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	126	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	34.94	34.90	2.14	2.13	93	75	75	100
7.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	98	95	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	41.22	41.17	3.25	3.27	140	170	160	175
8.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	114	75	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	41.20	41.17	3.28	3.27	100	108	100	102
9.	3-Methyl-2,4-TNP	132	85	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₄	35.85	35.89	2.50	2.56	75	82	80	75
10.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	100	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₄ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	31.49	31.58	1.65	1.66	83	88	80	84
11.	2-Chloro-3-bromo-4,6-DNP	185	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	28.15	28.19	1.50	1.48	182	93	80	85
12.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	118	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	36.95	37.00	2.58	2.65	100	91	98	95
13.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	121	65	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	32.90	32.85	2.35	2.33	109	92	109	110
14.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	105	75	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	36.98	37.00	2.60	2.65	170	185	220	184
15.	4-Chloro-5-methyl-2,6-DNP	117	95	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₈ S ₄	36.94	37.00	2.64	2.65	75	80	81	83

DNP and TNP refers to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected. AN, AT, HS and CG refers to *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Colleotrichum gloeosporide* respectively.

TABLE 2—ESTERS OF N,N'-METHYL-PIPERIZINO DITHIOFORMIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		Dosages required for the inhibition of 50% of growth of $\mu\text{ gm/cm}^2$			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	AN	AT	HS	CG
1.	2,4-DNP	90	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	42.88	42.85	4.12	4.16	115	125	108	110
2.	2,6-DNP	105	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	42.85	42.85	4.16	4.16	110	102	104	103
3.	2,4,6-DNP	96	85	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	37.16	37.22	3.42	3.36	100	75	80	100
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	115	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	38.47	38.51	3.45	3.50	70	75	76	77
5.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	110	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	38.51	38.51	3.48	3.50	180	175	150	145
6.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	98	90	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	38.59	38.51	3.42	3.50	75	100	75	76
7.	2-Methyl-4,6-DNP	112	90	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	43.72	43.70	4.42	4.49	185	175	180	182
8.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	85	83	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	43.75	43.70	4.51	4.49	150	142	180	175
9.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	120	85	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	43.70	43.70	4.43	4.49	88	130	80	135
10.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	200d	72	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₆ S ₂	38.88	38.90	3.71	3.74	105	100	102	125
11.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	100	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	35.46	35.44	2.90	2.95	100	75	75	77
12.	2-Chloro-5-bromo-4,6-DNP	114	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ClBrN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	31.73	31.71	2.58	2.64	115	100	102	85
13.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	122	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	40.05	40.00	3.75	3.79	86	83	82	80
14.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	111	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ BrN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	35.86	35.94	3.48	3.46	88	83	88	88
15.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	105	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	39.98	40.00	3.82	3.79	125	120	120	125
16.	4-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-DNP	116	73	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ O ₄ S ₂	40.02	40.00	3.80	3.79	83	100	106	110

DNP and TNP refers to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected. AN, AT, HS and CG refers to *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Colleotrichum gloeosporide* respectively.

TABLE 3—ESTERS OF N,N'-PHENYL-PIPERIZINO DITHIOFORMIC ACIDS

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol formula	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		Dosages required for the inhibition of 50% of growth in $\mu\text{gm}/\text{cm}^2$			
					Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	AN	AT	HS	CG
1.	2,4-DNP	65	70	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	59.45	59.49	3.95	3.96	150	135	145	160
2.	2,6-DNP	85	75	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	59.47	59.49	3.92	3.96	101	115	102	101
3.	2,4,6-DNP	115	72	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_5\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	45.40	45.53	3.32	3.34	100	85	100	100
4.	2-Chloro-4,6-DNP	103	80	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	46.48	46.47	3.40	3.42	85	80	80	85
5.	3-Chloro-4,6-DNP	117	90	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	46.59	46.57	3.45	3.42	180	275	250	250
6.	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	92	85	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	46.55	46.57	3.42	3.42	90	90	85	80
7.	3-Methyl-4,6-DNP	128	92	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	51.59	51.67	4.12	4.16	175	135	170	150
8.	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	112	87	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	51.68	51.67	4.17	4.16	105	150	101	101
9.	3-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	121	78	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_6\text{S}_2$	44.44	44.46	3.65	3.67	100	85	100	90
10.	2,3-Dichloro-4,6-DNP	127	72	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	43.15	43.17	2.88	2.90	100	115	100	100
11.	2-Chloro-3-bromo-4,6-DNP	165d	83	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClBrN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	39.52	39.53	2.70	2.71	105	120	150	105
12.	2-Chloro-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	126	90	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	47.80	47.80	3.75	3.76	85	85	100	90
13.	2-Bromo-5-methyl-4,6-DNP	119	85	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	41.52	41.53	3.40	3.42	90	90	100	100
14.	3-Chloro-2-methyl-4,6-DNP	115	90	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	47.75	47.80	3.78	3.76	150	300	180	135
15.	4-Chloro-5-methyl-2,6-DNP	100	85	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$	47.80	47.80	3.72	3.76	100	90	120	100

DNP and TNP refers to dinitro and trinitrophenyl respectively. All melting points are uncorrected.

AN, AT, HS and CG refers to *Aspergillus niger*, *Alternaria tenuis*, *Helminthosporium sativum* and *Colleotrichum gloeosporide* respectively.

Results and Discussion

The fungitoxicity of the esters of N-substituted dithioformic acids depends on both the ester moiety and the dithioformate moiety. In the ester moiety the fungitoxicity increases sharply when halogen atom and/or nitro group are placed at the ortho and/or para position in the phenyl ring (Table 1, No. 1 to 6). However, a halogen atom at the meta position seems to decrease fungitoxicity, possibly to the its-T effect (Table 1, No. 5). The effect of methyl group on fungitoxicity is rather abnormal, when present at the ortho or meta position in the phenyl ring of the ester moiety, decreases fungitoxicity (Table 2, No. 7 and 8). However, at para position to fungitoxicity is increased (Table 2, No. 9).

On the basis of these results, it is concluded that the esters of N-substituted dithioformic acids containing electronegative groups in the ester moiety at positions, where they can exert a weakening effect on the ester linkage, enhance toxicity, by aiding de-esterification inside the cells. The dithioformic acid thus formed, then reacts with the active component of the living tissue, thus destroying their contribution to the life process.

In the dithioformate moiety, the presence of electron donating groups increases the toxicity, N,N'-methyl, is more toxic than N,N'-phenyl-piperizino-dithioformic acids. Similarly the presence of two dithioformate-group in one molecule considerably increases the toxicity. During the presence investigations it has been observed that the fungitoxicity fall in the following order (Table 1, 2 and 3).

Experimental

Sodium salts of N-substituted dithioformic acids :

A solution of 2-methyl-piperizino (.01 M) in methyl alcohol (25 ml) is added with stirring to an ice cold solution of sodium hydroxide (.01 M) in water (10 ml) and with vigorous shaking and maintaining the temperature below 5°. The mixture is then stirred for another one hour below 10°. The product is

filtered and crystallised from methyl alcohol to give colourless crystals.

Halogeno-nitrophenyl Esters of N-substituted dithioformic acids :

A solution of halogenonitrobenzene (.01 M) in ethanol is added dropwise with stirring to a 10% solution of sodium salt of N-substituted dithioformic acids in ethyl alcohol keeping the temperature below 5°. The reaction mixture is stirred until the product separated. The ester is filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol. Their melting points, yields and analytical data are recorded in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

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